

AI-Enhanced Seamless Handover in Wi-Fi Networks with Multi-Link Management

Elena Ferrari
University of Padova
Padova, Italy
elena.ferrari.7@phd.unipd.it

Dave Cavalcanti
Intel Corporation
Hillsboro, Oregon, USA
dave.cavalcanti@intel.com

Valerio Frascolla
Intel Deutschland GmbH
Neubiberg, Germany
valerio.frascolla@intel.com

Rafael Rosales
Intel Deutschland GmbH
Neubiberg, Germany
rafael.rosales@intel.com

Abstract—This work presents an innovative Multi-Parameter Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based decision algorithm, designed to optimize handovers in Wi-Fi networks supporting Multi-Link Operation (MLO). The algorithm employs a two-step Neural Network (NN) architecture to facilitate efficient handover processes, integrating a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) NN with a Classification NN. The former predicts key performance indicators, which are then used by the latter to determine the optimal connection between a Wi-Fi Station and available Access Points. Our approach, compared to traditional distance-based handover, effectively improves connectivity in more complex and realistic curvilinear trajectories.

Index Terms—AI, Wi-Fi, Handover, Multi-Link Operation, Long-Short-Term Memory, Classification Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in developing efficient strategies to manage handovers, often initiated by user mobility within large areas like industrial manufacturing sites or smart cities [1]. Specifically, in the context of IEEE 802.11 (Wi-Fi) networks, horizontal handover ensures smooth traffic transition between Stations (STAs) and Access Points (APs), for continuous and reliable wireless connections [2].

In this scenario, most handover optimization strategies rely on a single metric, e.g., distance between STA and APs or Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI). However, due to the complexity of mobility environments influenced by numerous other metrics like latency, Signal-To-Noise Ratio (SNR), interference, and throughput across multiple links, we propose the Multi-Parameter Artificial Intelligence-based Decision (MPAID) algorithm, which better captures connection states and outperforms traditional distance-based methods.

The Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Neural Network (NN) of the MPAID uses distance of STAs from each AP, their coordinates, speed, and direction of movement to forecast predictive metrics (latency, SNR, and RSSI for each AP) for future time intervals. These predictions serve as inputs to the Classification NN, which decides the optimal AP to connect to the STA. Hence, MPAID highlights the advantages

This study was carried out within the PNRR research activities of the consortium iNEST (Interconnected North-Est Innovation Ecosystem) funded by the EU Next-GenerationEU (Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR) – Missione 4 Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – D.D. 1058 23/06/2022, ECS_00000043), and also partially funded by the EC Horizon Europe SNS JU PREDICT-6G (GA 101095890) and MULTIX (GA 101192521) Projects.

of using AI to manage the handover decision process, utilizing multiple metrics to enhance the selection of APs for improved connectivity and reliability.

In addition, we enhance the handover process exploiting the Multi-Link Operation (MLO) feature [3], which, introduced by the IEEE 802.11be (Wi-Fi 7) standard [4], [5], enables wireless devices, known as Multi-Link Devices (MLDs), to operate on multiple links simultaneously, minimizing interruptions during handover and improving throughput and reliability [6].

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews handover optimization in wireless networks; Section 3 details our novel AI-based approach; Section 4 outlines the experimental setup and results compared to a baseline; Section 5 summarizes the paper and suggests future work.

II. BACKGROUND AND STATE-OF-THE-ART

According to the IEEE 802.11 standard, the handover process involves two main steps [7]:

- 1) Discovery: The STA searches for potential APs to connect with using the *scan* function of the Medium Access Control (MAC) layer, which involves listening for beacon messages on designated channels. Based on the RSSI, the STA prioritizes a list of APs. Scanning can be either passive, where the STA only listens to beacon frames, or active, where the STA also sends probe requests and receives responses from APs.
- 2) Reauthentication: Authentication and re-association with the new AP are performed, by transferring credentials and other state information from the previous AP.

Handover optimization decisions are often based on a single metric, whereas NNs offer a promising alternative by enabling the simultaneous consideration of multiple metrics. NNs, with advanced predictive capabilities and complex data processing, can enhance handover efficiency, optimizing decision-making and overall connection quality, thus becoming increasingly relevant across different areas. For example, in autonomous vehicles, NNs are crucial for interpreting sensor data from cameras, LiDAR and radar to make informed decisions about navigation, obstacle avoidance, and safety [8], [9]. In industrial automation, they improve predictive maintenance, operational optimization, and quality control, e.g., as shown in [10] where an AI algorithm is presented to monitor and predict gas imbalances in distribution systems. NNs are also used

for security, as proposed in [11], where an algorithm that combines Convolutional NN (CNN) and LSTM is used to improve industrial system defenses against Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks. In smart cities, NNs help in traffic management, energy distribution, and public safety, while in healthcare NNs are used to analyze medical images or predict health status as shown in [12], where LSTM is employed to increase performance and accuracy in action recognition tasks using sensor data from gyroscopes and accelerometers.

In the field of communication, diverse NN-based approaches have been proposed to optimize handover procedures. In [13] authors propose a cloud-based architecture that deploys a more efficient split of functionalities in a Wi-Fi network, allowing for a more robust and faster handover procedure. In [14] a Gittins index-based framework is introduced to find an optimal stop of fractional Markovian multi-objective selections procedures, often employed in handover decisions. In [15], a novel CNN structure is compared with LSTM structures and measured Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) values are used to determine whether to perform or not a handover. In [16] authors propose a more concrete method to predict the probability of upcoming handovers in Wi-Fi networks using a machine learning approach to monitor RSSI patterns over time. In [17] authors use a multi-step time-series prediction approach with a random forest algorithm to address handover prediction, reducing unnecessary handovers by 60% compared to the RSS method. In [18], an anticipation-based handover solution using a Kalman filter is introduced, allowing proactive scanning and handover execution when better APs are available; however, this approach is limited by its reliance on RSSI alone. Similarly, [19] proposes the selection of the closest AP through a positioning process that prioritizes the AP with the shortest geometric distance to the STA; although straightforward, this method overlooks factors like network load, RSSI, or latency. Also [20] neglects other key metrics, focusing only on maximizing throughput considering the AP load and the available bandwidth. Similarly in [21] the handover decision is based only on the distance between the STA and the APs. Handover challenges have recently attracted research interest in mixed terrestrial-satellite networks, where efficient management across diverse access networks is particularly difficult. For instance, [22] integrates a multi-criteria based vertical handover technique for efficient handover among Wi-Fi, cellular and satellite networks. Finally, a very recent survey of handover optimization approaches in Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) can be found in [23].

Other works focus on enhancing Wi-Fi features to ensure reliable operations in noisy industrial environments. Authors in [24] extend the Wi-Fi 802.11CB standard and demonstrate how multi-radio redundancy capabilities can achieve zero-delay roaming for mobile robots. Authors in [25] exploit Digital Twins (DTs) to moving STAs in Wi-Fi supporting MLO to perform seamless roaming between APs. Authors in [26] look at the MLO feature from the energy consumption point of view, proposing a framework to reduce the overall system energy budget. Authors in [27] propose a low-cost

experimental platform to learn how to optimize Wi-Fi features in industrial environments. Finally, [28] introduces an LSTM-based model that focuses only on predicting the RSRP metric. Unlike previous methods that use a single metric, overlooking key factors affecting wireless links quality and reliability, our approach extends LSTM to predict multiple Key Performance Indicators, (KPIs), e.g., latency, SNR, and RSSI, thus offering advantages that collectively enhance connection quality.

III. MPAID ALGORITHM

Our MPAID algorithm presents a two-step NN architecture, using an LSTM network and a Classification NN, as shown in Fig. 1. It leverages predictive capabilities of the LSTM to estimate KPIs, which are subsequently processed by the Classification NN to enable proactive handover decisions, assisting the STA in predicting the best target AP.

Fig. 2 provides a schematic overview of this process, while the pseudocode of the novel algorithm is detailed in Alg. 1.

Fig. 1: MPAID algorithm logic.

A task queue system supports concurrent task execution using a thread-safe queue to manage tasks in a multi-threaded scenario. It involves a continuous data collection process that captures data every 10ms. Once 10 sequences of data are collected, the algorithm proceeds with pre-processing the data, applies the LSTM model to such pre-processed data, and calls the Classification NN to the predictions provided by the LSTM model. Hence, network flow adjustments are made based on the output of the Classification NN. Monitoring and logging tasks are integral to track system performance and record key data for analysis. Hence, while task management is overseen by a dedicated thread that continuously monitors the task queue, ensuring controlled task execution, preventing race conditions, and maintaining thread safety, the task enqueueing mechanism locks the queue, adds tasks, and alerts the processing thread, facilitating task handling and preserving system responsiveness.

To assess the effectiveness of MPAID in Wi-Fi networks supporting MLO, KPIs such as latency, packet delivery ratio (PDR), i.e., the ratio of packets received to packets sent, and the number of handovers between APs are compared against a baseline, i.e., the widely used distance-based algorithm.

Fig. 2: Numbered boxes depict the MPAID sequential data flow through the processing pipeline. Blue-bordered ones indicate the coordination and distribution of tasks from the task queue to relevant components, red-bordered ones the execution and management of tasks by the management system.

A. Development and Training of the LSTM model

Data collection involves simulations where the STA moves in 2D space along linear and curvilinear trajectories, varying velocity and initial position to develop a robust NN model. The starting position of the STA and its velocities are generated randomly, ensuring the STA moves in an area of 2500m². Regarding curvilinear motion, the most common movements in manufacturing sites are taken into account, e.g., circular, arc, elliptical, and spiral paths. To ensure comprehensive data acquisition for both APs, each simulation is executed twice using the distance-based approach: first, with the STA connecting to the nearest AP, then to the farthest AP.

To effectively implement this approach, the system collects data from the last 10 time instants, each occurring every 10ms. Specifically, the controller captures the STA position (x_{STA}, y_{STA}) and velocity (v_x, v_y) . With known AP positions, the controller pre-processes data for the LSTM model by calculating distances to each AP, speed, and direction of the STA. Hence, the 6 input features of the LSTM model are the coordinates of the STA in a 2D space (x_{STA}, y_{STA}) , its speed given by $v = \sqrt{v_x^2 + v_y^2}$, and the direction of movement given by $\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{v_y}{v_x}\right)$. Also the distance between the STA and each AP are considered, i.e., $d_{STA,AP1}$ and $d_{STA,AP2}$ computed as $\sqrt{(x_{STA} - x_{AP_i})^2 + (y_{STA} - y_{AP_i})^2}$ with $i \in 1, 2$.

Algorithm 1 MPAID algorithm

```

1: Simulation starts → set "System in operation"
2: Data Collection:
3: Schedule data collection every 10 ms
4: while System in operation do
5:   Collect data:  $(x, y)$  STA position,  $(v_x, v_y)$  velocities
6:   if 10 sequences of values are collected then
7:     Add a data processing task to the queue
8:   end if
9: end while
10: Data Processing:
11: while A data processing task is in the queue do
12:   Compute distances between STA and each AP, compute velocity and direction of movement of the STA
13:   Organize the data into the 6 input features required by the LSTM model
14:   Normalize the pre-processed data
15: end while
16: LSTM Model Prediction:
17: Apply the LSTM model to predict future KPIs
18: Post Processing with Classification NN:
19: Use the Classification NN to determine the optimal AP for connection
20: if The predicted AP differs from the current AP then
21:   Add a handover task to the queue
22: end if
23: Network Flow Management:
24: if A handover task is present in the queue then
25:   Execute the handover task
26:   Disable the 3 links to the previous AP
27:   Enable the 3 links to the new AP
28:   Initiate network flow to the new AP
29: end if

```

The collected data are organized to provide a look-back of 10 time steps, with lat_{AP1} , SNR_{AP1} , $RSSI_{AP1}$, lat_{AP2} , SNR_{AP2} , $RSSI_{AP2}$ as KPIs, computed as mean values at constant intervals of 10ms. In particular, the latency is considered as the end-to-end (E2E) STA to AP latency; the RSSI, expressed in dBm, is computed using the free space path loss model that considers the STA and AP transmitted powers and positions; the SNR is calculated as the difference between the received signal power and the thermal noise power density at room temperature.

The complete data set, obtained by concatenating the data sets from each simulation run, is normalized using `StandardScaler`, scaling each feature individually. It was organized to ensure that each simulation is processed in separate batches, preventing data mixing between different simulations and allowing the model to learn independently of each simulation. The data set is divided into training, validation, and test sets in a 60 : 20 : 20 ratio. Using the pre-processed inputs, the LSTM model predicts KPIs for each AP over a 300ms prediction horizon. The selection of the look-back and prediction horizon values is guided by the trade-off

between the accuracy and the response time of the model. Using 10 past intervals to predict the next 30 offers an effective balance between real-time processing and prediction accuracy.

The LSTM architecture has two layers with a hidden size of 128, processing input sequences and generating hidden states via fully connected layers with Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation functions. The final output layer predicts KPIs and the model is trained using a masked mean square error (MSE) loss function to manage missing or invalid data points.

The selection of the hyperparameter values starts with values deemed reasonable based on previous research in the domain. These values are subsequently fine-tuned through an iterative process, guided by the performance metrics of the model, including prediction accuracy and loss function evaluation. This empirical approach facilitates the convergence to a local minimum, as validated by the performed simulations.

B. Development and Training of the Classification NN

For intelligent AP selection based on the predicted KPIs, the Classification NN maps KPI sequences from LSTM into one of two classes corresponding to AP1 or AP2, determining the optimal AP to connect with the STA. The dataset for training the NN includes KPIs values for each AP, previously used as target features for the LSTM model, i.e., lat_{AP1} , SNR_{AP1} , $RSSI_{AP1}$, lat_{AP2} , SNR_{AP2} , and $RSSI_{AP2}$.

Hence, the input to the Classification NN consists of temporal sequences of the previously predicted 6 features. Each sequence comprises 30 consecutive time steps, according to the prediction horizon of the LSTM model. Each input feature is individually standardized using the `StandardScaler`, ensuring uniform scaling throughout the dataset. This approach aligns with the normalization applied during LSTM training, thereby eliminating the need to re-normalize the predicted KPIs before feeding them into the classification network.

Classification labels are derived based on a score computed for each AP within a sequence window. The score is defined as the sum of SNR and RSSI, penalized by latency. In detail, a time sequence of network measurements for AP $i \in \{1, 2\}$ over a length window T , i.e., $T = 30$, is considered as:

$$s_i = \left\{ \left(\text{SNR}_i^{(t)}, \text{RSSI}_i^{(t)}, \text{lat}_i^{(t)} \right) \right\}_{t=1}^T$$

where $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$ represents discrete time steps in the considered time window, so that each s_i captures the SNR, RSSI and latency values observed for AP i at time step t .

A scoring function \mathcal{S}_i for each AP over the sequence is defined as:

$$\mathcal{S}_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\text{SNR}_i^{(t)} + \text{RSSI}_i^{(t)} - \text{lat}_i^{(t)} \right)$$

Hence, the classification label $y \in \{0, 1\}$ is assigned based on the AP with the highest score \mathcal{S}_i :

$$y = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \mathcal{S}_1 > \mathcal{S}_2 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Hence, the label is assigned to the AP with the highest average score across the sequence, enabling the model to learn to choose the AP with the best expected performance over the given time window. The data set is then split into training, validation and test sets in a ratio 60 : 20 : 20. The architecture of the Classification NN comprises 3 fully connected layers. ReLU activations are used between layers and the dropout is applied after each hidden layer for regularization. The model is improved by the Adam optimizer and uses the cross-entropy loss as the objective function. Hyper-parameter values are set empirically, as previously done with the LSTM model.

IV. RESULTS

The MPAID is implemented and validated in the ns3 network simulator, modeling the functional parameters and communication behaviors of the MLD STA and MLD APs, and employing static and mobile devices, thus creating a hybrid network. This network comprises a MLD STA, which interacts with 2 stationary MLD APs (AP1 and AP2), a server, and a remote control unit responsible for real-time network optimization. To increase the realism of the scenario and introduce network interference, two additional static MLD STAs, i.e., STA1 and STA2, are incorporated to facilitate multi-link operation. The network configuration used is illustrated in Fig. 3. Two different scenarios are considered: 1) STA1 and STA2 are not present; 2) STA1 and STA2 are added.

Fig. 3: ns3 network configuration and MLD internal structure.

In this configuration, the STAs act as a data source, continuously transmitting frames to the connected AP, using Wi-Fi 7 with MLO, allowing transmissions across 3 frequency bands, each with center frequencies of 2.4GHz, 5GHz, and 6GHz. The frames received by the APs are then sent to the server, which acts only as receiver, via Ethernet connections. Hence, the traffic is unidirectional, from the STA to the server. In the first scenario, despite MLO being supported, the mobile STA connects only to one AP at the time, and the choice to which AP the STA has to connect to is provided by the off-board controller, which is responsible for evaluating handovers and

determining the optimal AP for the STA through the proposed optimized approach. Instead in the second scenario, to add interference in the network and to make it more realistic, two additional static STAs are added, each communicating with one AP and maintaining the connection with them during all the simulation. In such case, the two additional STAs send frames using Variable Bit Rate (VBR).

Considered such an architecture, the network configuration parameters include:

- the transmission power, set to 17dBm for the STA and to 20dBm for the APs;
- two transmit and receive antennas for each node;
- the duration of the maximum transmission opportunity (txop) for APs and STA, set to 5600ms;
- the interval between consecutive beacon transmissions, required to maintain network synchronization and announcing to STA the AP presence and capabilities, which is equal to 102.4ms;
- the network load, set to 10Mbps.

Mobility is introduced only through the STA, which follows linear or curvilinear trajectories, while AP1 and AP2 remain fixed at coordinates (15, 15) and (15, 35), respectively, in a 2D space free from obstacles. In the second scenario, 2 stationary STAs are introduced, STA1 located at (5, 15) and STA2 at (30, 20). Each STA establishes communication with the nearest AP, with STA1 connecting to AP1 and STA2 to AP2. Hence, integrating the NN models into the ns3 simulator, together with multithreading for data processing and network flow management, supports accurate and responsive modeling of real-time decision-making processes.

To validate the effectiveness of the trained LSTM model, its prediction accuracy and generalization capability are thoroughly evaluated. Fig. 4 shows the training and validation loss curves, highlighting model convergence and marking the stage at which the model reliably generalizes to unseen data. Further insights into the ability of the model to predict KPIs are presented, for both linear and curvilinear trajectories, in Fig. 5, where the measured KPIs are shown in orange and the predicted ones in blue. A careful analysis of the figure reveals a minor discrepancy in some KPI values, which highlights an opportunity for refinement in future research. In fact, by integrating real-world parameters into the model, these discrepancies can be further minimized, enhancing the accuracy of the KPI predictions.

The training and validation losses of the classification NN are shown in Fig. 6 while, in Fig. 7, the associate confusion matrix is depicted. This matrix highlights the discrepancies between the ground truth and the predicted labels, the former determined using the distance-based method. The confusion matrix demonstrates the precision of the proposed Classification NN, which reaches 99.93%, indicating the robustness of the model in accurately classifying the data.

To assess the performance of the proposed optimized approach based on NN models, a comparative analysis focusing on average latency throughout the simulations is conducted,

Fig. 4: Train and Validation losses of the LSTM NN.

for both considered scenarios. The MPAID algorithm is compared with a baseline method in which handover decisions are based solely on distance. To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, 100 different test simulations are performed for both scenarios. In detail, in the second scenario the metrics are referred only to the packets sent from the mobile STA. In these simulations, the STA starts moving from various initial positions and with different velocities, generating linear and curvilinear trajectories.

Table I compares average performance metrics of MPAID vs the traditional distance-based method, in scenarios with and without the 2 additional static STAs, in both linear and curvilinear trajectories. The performance metrics evaluated include average latency, latency standard deviation, average number of switches, and PDR.

Table Ia shows comparable performances: E2E values are nearly identical (495329.60ms vs 495921.64ms), differing only by 592ms. Both methods also show the same average number of handovers and PDR values, indicating limited impact in this scenario. Despite this, the AI-approach outperforms the distance-based method in 60% of the simulation runs.

Table Ib shows a clear performance improvement of the MPAID algorithm, as the average E2E latency is reduced by 4.86ms, an improvement of 76.90% against the distance-based method. This reduction aligns with the observed decrease in the average number of handovers, indicating that our solution effectively avoids unnecessary switches between APs when the STA moves rapidly across their coverage areas. Furthermore, it should be noted that the LSTM model achieves a PDR of 93.1%, while the distance-based method achieves a slightly higher PDR of 94.27%. This suggests that while the MPAID algorithm significantly reduces latency and handovers, there is a marginal trade-off in terms of packet delivery efficiency. Overall, taking into account only curvilinear trajectories, the MPAID algorithm outperforms the distance-based method in 73.33% of the simulation runs.

In the more realistic second scenario, which includes interference, Table Ic illustrates that the MPAID algorithm delivers results comparable to those of the distance-based

(a) Linear trajectory.

(b) Curvilinear trajectory.

Fig. 5: Predicted KPIs (in blue) provided by the LSTM model against the ones measured using the distance-based one (in orange) for linear and curvilinear trajectories. If no values are represented, the AP was not used at that specific timestamp.

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPAID Handover	0.50	0.18	97.43	1
Distance-based Handover	0.50	0.18	97.57	1

(a) First scenario: Linear trajectories

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPAID Handover	0.62	0.41	94.90	1
Distance-based Handover	0.62	0.41	92.55	1

(c) First scenario: Linear trajectories

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPAID Handover	1.46	2.75	93.10	1.19
Distance-based Handover	6.32	12.89	94.27	2.44

(b) First scenario: Curvilinear trajectories

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPAID Handover	2.25	4.14	93.04	1.32
Distance-based Handover	4.04	10.28	91.90	2.11

(d) Second scenario: Curvilinear trajectories

TABLE I: Comparison of MPAID vs distance-based handovers across the two scenarios, evaluating average latency, latency standard deviation, PDR, and number of handovers for both linear and curvilinear trajectories.

Fig. 6: Train and Validation losses of the Classification NN.

method. The E2E latency values are almost indistinguishable, with the MPAID algorithm recording $618048.91ns$ and the distance-based method $618759.47ns$, resulting in a minimal difference of roughly $711ns$. Furthermore, both approaches exhibit the same average number of handovers; however, the

Fig. 7: Confusion Matrix showing discrepancies between the ground truth and predicted classified labels.

MPAID algorithm demonstrates a higher PDR compared to the distance-based approach and outperforms the distance-based approach in 56% of the simulation runs.

Finally, Table Id highlights a significant improvement in performance achieved by the MPAID algorithm, evidenced by a reduction in the average E2E latency of $1.789ms$. This

improvement corresponds to a decrease in the average number of handovers and a higher PDR value. Focusing on curvilinear trajectories, the MPAID algorithm outperforms the distance-based method in 56% of the simulation trials.

Hence, even with interference, the proposed MPAID algorithm improves performances.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Our study introduces a new optimized approach for horizontal handovers over Wi-Fi with MLO. Experimental results demonstrate that our approach reduces both E2E latency and average handover count, outperforming the distance-based baseline in both scenarios considered, even when interference is taken into consideration. In fact, when the STA moves rapidly across the overlapping coverage of the two APs, keeping the link with a single AP proves to be more efficient than executing frequent handovers.

In future work we could consider a more general and flexible solution, adaptable to both network load conditions, varying numbers of STAs and APs and adding more interference on the network to achieve higher improvements. Moreover, we could use the planned Wi-Fi 8 feature that allows for separate management of each link, thus enabling the STA to maintain simultaneous connections to both APs, switching only when one AP offers much higher performance than the other.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Rehman, et al, "A Survey of Handover Management in Mobile HetNets: Current Challenges and Future Directions," *Applied Sciences*, 13(5), 3367, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13053367>.
- [2] S. Pahal and P. Nandal, "Handover challenges in wireless communications and their solutions," *International conference on innovative computing and communication (ICICC)*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4749805>.
- [3] Á. López-Raventós and B. Bellalta, "Multi-Link Operation in IEEE 802.11be WLANs," in *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 94-100, August 2022, doi:10.1109/MWC.006.2100404.
- [4] C. Deng et al., "IEEE 802.11be Wi-Fi 7: New Challenges and Opportunities," in *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 2136-2166, Fourthquarter 2020, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2020.3012715.
- [5] V. Frascolla et al., "Wi-Fi Evolution: The Path Towards Wi-Fi 7 and Its Impact on IIoT," *Journal of Mobile Multimedia*, 19(01), 263-276, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.13052/jmm1550-4646.19113>.
- [6] J. Zhang et al., "Synchronous Multi-Link Access in IEEE 802.11be: Modeling and Network Sum Rate Optimization," *ICC 2022 - IEEE International Conference on Communications*, pp. 2309-2314, May 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/icc45855.2022.9838923>.
- [7] A. Mishra et al., "An Empirical Analysis of the IEEE 802.11 MAC Layer Handoff Process," *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 93-102, Apr. 2003, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1145/956981.956990>.
- [8] N. Kunchakuri, "MATLAB-Based Simulation of Generative AI-Based Autonomous Vehicle Control for High-Speed Driving and Emergency Maneuvers," *2025 1st Int. Conf. on Advances in Computer Science, Electrical, Electronics, and Communication Technologies (CE2CT)*, Bhimtal, Nainital, India, 2025, pp. 1191-1196, doi: 10.1109/CE2CT64011.2025.10939159.
- [9] B. Škugor, et al, "Interaction-Aware Optimal Safe Speed Control for Autonomous Vehicles Approaching Unsignalized Crosswalks With Pedestrians," in *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, doi: 10.1109/TCST.2025.3561056.
- [10] A. K. Petrova and A. M. Sinitca, "Application of Neural Networks in the Tasks of Automation at Industrial Enterprises," *2021 IEEE Conference of Russian Young Researchers in Electrical and Electronic Engineering (EIConRus)*, St. Petersburg, Moscow, Russia, 2021, pp. 577-581, doi: 10.1109/EIConRus51938.2021.9396114.
- [11] W. Wei et al., "A DDOS Attack Traffic Classification Model for Industrial Internet Based on CNN-LSTM," *2022 China Automation Congress (CAC)*, Xiamen, China, 2022, pp. 3443-3448, doi: 10.1109/CAC57257.2022.10055418.
- [12] M. Kandpal et al., "Human Activity Recognition in Smart Cities from Smart Watch Data using LSTM Recurrent Neural Networks," *2023 1st International Conference on Advanced Innovations in Smart Cities (ICAISC)*, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, 2023, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICAISC56366.2023.10085688.
- [13] V. M. G. Martinez et al., "Ultra Reliable Communication for Robot Mobility enabled by SDN Splitting of WiFi Functions," *2018 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*, Natal, Brazil, 2018, pp. 00527-00530, doi: 10.1109/ISCC.2018.8538603.
- [14] L. Di Gregorio and V. Frascolla, "Handover Optimality in Heterogeneous Networks," *2019 IEEE 2nd 5G World Forum (5GWF)*, Dresden, Germany, 2019, pp. 365-370, doi: 10.1109/5GWF.2019.8911617.
- [15] A. C. Büyüksirin et al., "Handover Method Based on Time Series Analysis," *2023 31st Signal Processing and Communications Applications Conference (SIU)*, Istanbul, Turkiye, 2023, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/SIU59756.2023.10223764.
- [16] M. Feltrin and S. Tomasin, "A Machine-Learning-Based Handover Prediction for Anticipatory Techniques in Wi-Fi Networks," *2018 10th Int. Conf. on Ubiquitous and Future Networks (ICUFN)*, Prague, Czech Republic, 2018, pp. 341-345, doi: 10.1109/ICUFN.2018.8436796.
- [17] M.A. Khan et al., "ML-Based Handover Prediction and AP Selection in Cognitive Wi-Fi Networks," *Journal of Network and Systems Management*, vol. 30, no. 4, Aug. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10922-022-09684-2>.
- [18] N. Montavont et al., "Handover triggering in IEEE 802.11 networks," *2015 IEEE 16th International Symposium on A World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks (WoWMoM)*, Boston, MA, USA, 2015, pp. 1-9, doi: 10.1109/WoWMoM.2015.7158126.
- [19] M. Zaidi et al., "Reducing Wi-Fi handover delay using a new positioning process," *2011 International Conference on Communications, Computing and Control Applications (CCCA)*, Hammamet, Tunisia, 2011, doi: 10.1109/CCCA.2011.6031469.
- [20] U. Shafi et al., "An Optimal Distributed Algorithm for Best AP Selection and Load Balancing in WiFi," *2018 15th International Conference on Smart Cities: Improving Quality of Life Using ICT & IoT (HONET-ICT)*, Islamabad, Pakistan, 2018, pp. 65-69, doi: 10.1109/HONET.2018.8551335.
- [21] P. Avila-Campos et al., "Optimizing Handover in Time-Sensitive Wi-Fi Networks through Machine Learning," *2024 IEEE 29th International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, Padova, Italy, 2024, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/ETFA61755.2024.10710709.
- [22] A. S. Gaur et al., "Vertical Handover Decision for Mobile IoT Edge Gateway Using Multi-Criteria and Fuzzy Logic Techniques," *Advances in Internet of Things*, vol. 10, no. 04, pp. 57-93, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.4236/ait.2020.104005>.
- [23] S. Jahandar et al., "Handover decision with multi-access edge computing in 6G networks: A survey," *Results in Engineering*, Volume 25, 2025, 103934, ISSN 2590-1230, Elsevier.
- [24] S. Sudhakaran et al., "Zero-Delay Roaming for Mobile Robots Enabled by Wireless TSN Redundancy," *2023 IEEE 19th International Conference on Factory Communication Systems (WFCS)*, Pavia, Italy, 2023, doi: 10.1109/WFCS57264.2023.10144124.
- [25] S. Scanzio et al., "Multi-Link Operation and Wireless Digital Twin to Support Enhanced Roaming in Next-Gen Wi-Fi," *2024 IEEE 20th International Conference on Factory Communication Systems (WFCS)*, Toulouse, France, 2024, doi: 10.1109/WFCS60972.2024.10540931.
- [26] N. Dawar et al., "Enhancing Wi-Fi 7: Traffic Flow Intelligence and Multi-Link Operation for Optimal Efficiency," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 63298-63309, 2025, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3557435.
- [27] M. Rosani et al., "A Software Platform for Testing Multi-Link Operation in Industrial Wi-Fi Networks," *2024 IEEE 20th International Conference on Factory Communication Systems (WFCS)*, Toulouse, France, 2024.
- [28] Y. Kanto and K. Watabe, "Wireless Link Quality Estimation Using LSTM Model," *NOMS 2024-2024 IEEE Network Operations and Management Symposium*, Seoul, Korea, Republic of, 2024, pp. 1-5.